

The Description of Information System Analysis and Design (September 2021)

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Abstract— An information system is a man-made system that consists of components inside an organization that allow information to be presented. A solid information system may increase the performance of all corporate operations that are backed by accurate and safe data, allowing all activities to function more efficiently. Manufacturing businesses may enhance their performance by being more effective and efficient. The use of web-based apps can help to accomplish these advantages. PT X is one of Indonesia's leading cement makers, and in order to preserve its competitive edge, the company established multiple Process Laboratories to oversee product quality control. Process Laboratory IV is one of them. Process Laboratory IV continues to use a spreadsheet-based information system, which means that the majority of operations and evaluations are still done by hand. Slow information flow rates, minimum levels of information security, and the possibility for different types of fraud are all still problems. The goal of this study was to develop a more efficient quality control information system through the use of a web-based application. Building: (a) Business process diagrams, (b) Use case diagrams, (c) Class diagrams, (d) Entity relationship diagrams, and (e) Databases, followed by web-based application design based on the information system design findings. To reduce information security problems, the system architecture includes four actors with varying levels of power and access. Various types of fraud can also be reduced under these settings. Furthermore, the system architecture enhances information flow efficiency by removing the need to re-enter set point data. It can be stated that the use of web-based applications in the design of information systems has helped increase efficiency and mitigate the shortcomings of present information systems in the PT X Process Laboratory IV.

Index Terms—Information, System, Organization, Efficient, Operation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing industry groups are inextricably linked to this. The performance of management in regulating the manufacturing industry's production system will be influenced by an effective and effectively implemented information system. Information systems that are overly complex and difficult to use, on the other hand, might impair the overall efficiency of a manufacturing system. The use of web-based apps is common. Web-based apps are frequently utilized to improve a process's efficacy and efficiency. Its applications are numerous, including boosting learning efficiency, reducing electrical energy usage at home, and collecting survey data. The

improvement in efficiency is due to the fact that web-based applications make it easier for system actors to complete their duties. PT X is one of Indonesia's cement companies, and in order to retain its competitive edge, it has developed numerous Process Laboratories, one of which is the Process IV Laboratory, which is responsible for quality control operations.

Spreadsheets are still used to support the information system at the Process IV Laboratory. As a result, the majority of operations and assessments are done manually, slowing down the flow of data. Furthermore, due to the lack of security features integrated into the program, the usage of spreadsheets opens the door to numerous types of fraud.

As a result, the creation of a supporting application for Process IV Laboratory quality control is required as a step toward improving the system's efficiency and dependability. Another anticipated beneficial effect is the streamlining of data and information flow. The system is made up of interconnected components or a network of procedures that operate together to achieve certain goals or objectives

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The definition of an information system may be inferred from the definitions of its constituent terms, which are system and information. The system, according to Anggraini and Zega, is a collection of numerous parts or elements that interact to achieve a certain objective. Definition Jogiyanto said the same idea, describing a system as "a network of interrelated work for performing an activity or achieving a certain objective."

A system can consist of a collection of people, machines, objects, or other sorts of entities. Meanwhile, information is the outcome of processing data with a certain value or meaning. Leitch and Davis define an information system as a system that connects the daily transaction processing needs, support operations, management activities, and strategies within an organization to provide the required reports for both internal and external purposes, based on the definitions of the two words.

An information system is the outcome of human design and consists of many components inside an organization that work together to achieve a common purpose, which is to provide meaningful information. One component of the organization's requirements is information systems. The efficacy and

efficiency of the system information utilized by the organization represents whether the organization is moving forward or backward. Leman. The following are some of the general information system objectives: (1) provide information to assist process management decision making; (2) simplify daily operations; and (3) provide information appropriate for parties outside the organization, particularly regarding issue management transparency.

The description of the analysis and design of information systems is divided into several parts, this chapter will discuss systems analysis and system design, information systems development life cycle (SDLC), rapid application development (RAD), computer-based software engineering tools (CASE), methodologies agile and eXtreme programming, object-oriented analysis and design, and rational integrated processes (RUP).

A. System analysis and system designs

Systems analysis is a term that collectively describes the early phases of systems development. Systems analysis is a problem-solving technique that describes components by studying how well their component parts work and interact to achieve their goals. Systems design is a complementary problem-solving technique that re-elevates component parts into a complete system, hopefully an improved system. This shows the addition, deletion, and change of parts relative to the initial system.

B. Information Systems Development Life Cycle (SDLC)

From conception to implementation, software development must go through various stages. Problems with the system emerge after the program or system has been incorporated in its development. The Systems Development Life Cycle is the name for this cycle (SDLC). The Systems Development Life Cycle (SDLC) is a framework for creating information systems. The information system development life cycle is a diagram that depicts the major phases and steps involved in the creation of a system.

The development of a new system or its development will start from the planning stage again. The following is an explanation of the system development life cycle:

a. Planning Stage

System development planning basically aims to identify and prioritize the system to be developed. What targets are achieved, the duration of the process, and consider the need for funds used in system development.

b. Analysis Stage

At this stage of analysis, collect any business needs from various interested stakeholders. Define business needs that will be followed up to be accommodated by the system to be built. Create a simple prototype to meet these needs. Prioritizing the business needs that have been defined. Create and evaluate alternative solutions for each of these needs. Review solution recommendations with management.

c. Design

Do the design by integrating it with the network. Designing the application architecture to be used. Design the screen

display for the user. Designing system interfaces. Design and integrate systems with databases. Make prototypes for design details. Create and integrate systems with control systems

d. Implementation

Build software components. Verify and test the completed system. Perform data conversion. Train users to interact and complete their work tasks using the system. Make documentation of the system that has been built in the form of a manual book.

e. Activity

Perform system maintenance by checking periodically/periodically.

C. Rapid Application Development (RAD)

Rapid Application Development (RAD) is a term originally used to describe a software development process first developed and successfully used during the mid-1970s by the New York Telephone Co. Systems Development Center under the direction of Dan Gielan.

RAD is essentially a variation of the sequential release strategy. In addition it is very important to note that some technology suppliers claim that the development environment is sophisticated such as high-end programming languages, application development tools, and supporting technologies (CASE). If you wish, you may write in the first person singular or plural and use the active voice ("I observed that ..." or "We observed that ..." instead of "It was observed that ..."). Remember to check spelling. If your native language is not English, please get a native English-speaking colleague to carefully proofread your paper.

D. Computer Based Software Engineering Tool (CASE)

The diagramming tool allows graphical representation. Computer display and report generators help prototype how the system "looks and feels". IBM's Rational Product is the best known CASE tool. Analysis tools automatically check for consistency in charts, forms, and reports.

The central repository provides integrated storage of diagrams, reports, and project management specifications. Documentation generator standardizes technical and user documentation. The code generator enables the automatic generation of program and database code directly from design documents, diagrams, forms, and reports.

E. Computer Based Software Engineering Tool (CASE)

Graphical representation is possible using the diagramming tool. Computer display and report generators aid in prototyping how the system "feels" and "looks." The most well-known CASE tools are IBM's Rational Products. Charts, forms, and reports are automatically checked for consistency by analysis tools.

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and database code to be generated automatically from design papers, diagrams, forms, and reports.

F. Extreme Programming and Agile Methodology

Agile is a phrase used to represent a software development method that stresses incremental delivery, team communication, continuous planning, and continuous expenditure rather than attempting to provide everything at once at the end. Agile emphasizes lean procedures and the creation of viable beverage products (MVPs) that go through several iterations before being finalized.

Agile techniques are development and testing practices that emphasize continuous iteration throughout a project's software development cycle.

G. Object-Oriented Analysis and Design

When object-oriented programming is combined with an object-oriented Analysis and Design Process, it produces the best results. Object orientation is a software development strategy that is the pinnacle of identifying the most effective ways to construct systems. It is the method most frequently employed by software engineers today.

Students, aircraft wing surface control systems, sensors, and engines are all represented by objects. Objects can also symbolize an idea, such as a bank customer, a trademark, a wedding, or a simple listing. A class is a description of a collection of objects with common qualities, characteristics, and circumstances.

H. Integrated Rational Process (RUP)

Object-oriented analysis and design, as well as UML have a big effect on RUP. IBM purchased Rational software in 2003. Dynamic Perspective and Lifecycle Phases, Static Perspective, and Practice Perspective and Core Process are the three views in RUP. The phases of RUP fluctuate with time, as seen by the Dynamic Perspective and Lifecycle Phases. Static and Practice Perspectives are made up of things that do not change in order to continue trying to modify dynamic processes. The Practice Perspective is the result of successful implementation based on prior experience gained during the process.

III. DISCUSSION

1. Testing samples using X-ray and QCX equipment, giving data using spreadsheet software, and sending findings to review of Central Control Panel (CCP) personnel and operators are all part of the real information system used in Laboratory Process IV. In the information system, there are three operators who are actors. Operator 1 is in charge of the data input procedure. Operators 2 and 3 are in charge of quality control. The creation of the information system for the quality control process laboratory is primarily concerned with increasing the system's efficiency. Spreadsheets being replaced with web-based apps. The problem of Operator 1 repeating actions can be solved by using web-based apps. As a result, web-based apps are meant to not only serve as a replacement for spreadsheets, but also to improve the

information system in use. The Business Process Diagram may be used to demonstrate the design of system upgrades.

2. Business opportunities are exploited in the case study of tourism marketing by providing more effective product marketing through internet media to disseminate information about tourism transportation services island on Banana Island so that it can be widely known and provide economic benefits for the community Big Dipper fisherman on the Banana River. As a result, a marketing information system for island tourism in Indonesia Banana River is required in order to generate interest and increase the number of visitors. Data about island tourism on the Banana River was collected and kept in a MySQL-based database. This database is utilized in a marketing information system that has been built. In addition, the system marketing information for island tourism in Sungai Pisang, Padang, West Sumatra is meant to aid deep-diving fishermen in their marketing activities. To visit the Biduk Wisata marketing information system island, type biduakayah.com into a browser such as Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome, or Opera, and the home page will display.
3. In the Bangka Belitung region, MSMEs are still sold. Due to the restricted marketing area, MSME products are difficult to develop considerably. Changing sales tactics and strategies is one approach to increase the market share of MSME products. As a result, the goal of this study is to look at the variables that promote or discourage MSME business players in the Bangka Belitung Islands from using electronic commerce, or e-commerce. This application was created in line with the AHP idea of pairwise comparisons, in order to make the matrix computation process easier with the use of software. with a 33.2 percent weighting. These findings suggest that the technological restriction element, particularly information technology, is still crucial to address in order to improve the performance of MSME operators in the Bangka Belitung Islands using e-commerce. So that MSMEs may grow quickly thanks to the AHP application, which is aided by better information system architecture.
4. Warehouse management information systems based on CV. ABB have shown to be fairly successful in suppressing issues in warehouse management so far. Warehouse management becomes more accountable and transparent with CV. ABB's warehousing management information system. This may be observed in the usage of DFD in warehouse management, which makes it simpler to properly define the system and connect data components through data flows. The ERD encourages the use of display databases in information system architecture. ERD aids in the design and documenting of information so that the flow of components can be transmitted from one component to the next and data information can be delivered swiftly and clearly. By developing an information system with a clear and accurate order report and menus, the difficulty of warehouse management in terms of ordering replacement parts may be avoided. Warehouse data can be recorded properly with the use of ERD and DFD, where the components when the user enters the data are automatically documented by the system so that data manipulation and loss in terms of costs can be

minimized. System analysis and system design on this problem can be overcome with good planning, analysis, and implementation, so that the system in warehouse management can run well and smoothly.

5. The study's findings demonstrate that digital talent has a favorable relationship with Industry 4.0's Skills Revolution. The majority of innovation behavior indicators include ease with uncertainty, customer-centricity, entrepreneurial mentality, data-driven decision-making, cloud computing, SEO, web development, chief internet of things officer, data architect, data engineer, and data scientist. Skills Revolution Industry 4.0 critical thinking, monitoring, complex problem solving, leadership, analytical thinking, creativity, initiative, and responsibility are key indicators in the Skills Revolution Industry 4.0 architecture. In the construct of individual innovation behavior, produced indicators explore a new opportunity, champion new ideas, new idea implementation, and problem-solving ability. The Fourth Industrial Revolution (Industrie 4.0) is fast advancing. Mastering, digital knowledge, skills, and innovation will always be in demand. The demands of human resources in the world, which is totally digital, are also referred to as revolution development.

IV. CONCLUSION

The objective of an information system is to deliver valuable information. It is the outcome of human design and comprises of many components inside an organization. Because an organization or company will constantly be in contact with information, information systems are extremely vital and necessary for that organization or company.

In order to solve problems in a firm or organization, the design of information systems is critical. Systems definition, analysis, and design, information systems development life cycle (SDLC), rapid application development (RAD), computer-based software engineering tools (CASE), agile methodologies and Extreme programming, analysis and design oriented object, rational integrated process (RUP), BPD, ERD, and database were all discussed in the literature review. Improvements in the design of information systems are made using Business Process Diagrams (BPD) and Use Case Diagrams (UCD) to ensure that the data design process runs smoothly and that the risk of data fraud is minimized. The process of enhancing the design of information systems involves five stages: planning, analysis, design, implementation, and activity. This ensures that the information system's operations operate smoothly.

Furthermore, information system architecture prevents the common practice of repeating data point input sets. Eliminating these tasks cuts down on the time it takes to complete the full process, boosting system efficiency. Furthermore, eliminating looping reduces the risk of human mistake and data entry problems. As a result, it can be stated that the use of web-based applications in the design of information systems has aided in improving efficiency and effectiveness.

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